

CUDA-Driven Transport Solver Integrated into APOLLO3®

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ABSTRACT

The Method of Characteristics provides high-fidelity neutron-transport solutions, yet its 3D formulation remains computationally demanding therefore not well suited for industrial applications. This work introduces a GPU-accelerated solver for 3D-extruded MOC problems, fully integrated into the APOLLO3® deterministic code. Each 3D trajectory is assigned to a CUDA thread, and trajectories with similar characteristics are mapped to the same CUDA block, minimising warp divergence. The entire inner iteration, from source evaluation to convergence check, is executed on the GPU, avoiding any host-device data exchange. On an NVIDIA RTX A6000 the solver achieves up to 10× speed-up over a fully vectorised OpenMP baseline executed on a 96-core Xeon Gold 5220R node.

Keywords: Neutron transport, GPU acceleration, Method of Characteristics, APOLLO3®, CUDA

1. INTRODUCTION

APOLLO3® is a deterministic transport code developed at CEA with support from EDF and Framatome. The TDT (Two and Three Dimensional Transport) module implements a 2D based axially extruded 3D Method of Characteristics (MOC), making it particularly effective on heterogeneous HPC architectures [1].

Early developments of 3D MOC aimed at reducing the prohibitive memory footprint associated with extruded geometries. Chord-classification[2] and on-the-fly track reconstruction cut storage and sweep time. Subsequent work such as track decomposition and scheduling widely improved load balance and memory restraints without compromising accuracy [3, 4].

GPU offloading then emerged as a natural step. Kirschenmann *et al.* [5] demonstrated notable speed-ups for simplified P_N equations on early NVIDIA C870 hardware, while Zhou *et al.* [6] later ported full 3D MOC workflows to multi-GPU clusters. Recent micro-benchmarks on Volta-class devices suggest that the benefits of hand-tuned data placement is diminishing, favouring straight global-memory kernels that are easier to maintain.

Building on these insights, the present work offloads the entire MOC source-iteration loop to a single graphic card. By mapping one CUDA thread per 3D trajectory and grouping threads by common 2D trajectory and polar angle θ , the new solver outperforms a 96-core Xeon OpenMP by an order of magnitude, bringing industrial-scale 3D MOC analyses within practical reach.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 gathers the theoretical and implementation bases: it begins with a brief overview of the transport assumptions introduced for axially-extruded geometries, then details the 3D MOC formulation, the sweep algorithm, the fully GPU resident source iteration loop, and the CUDA parallelisation strategy. Section 3 reports the numerical results, comparing CPU and GPU performances on representative 5×5 and 7×7 PWR-assembly benchmarks and analysing the impact of tracking parameters. Finally, Section 4 presents the main conclusions and outlines avenues for future work.

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2. THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1. General description of the 3D-extruded Method Of Characteristics

The Method of Characteristics (MOC) solves the mono-energetic neutron transport equation in its integral form along straight trajectories within the spatial domain. This technique is particularly effective for unstructured meshes and complex geometries. In the TDT module of APOLLO3®, the solver implements an optimized formulation for 3D-extruded geometries derived from a transversal 2D mesh as shown in Fig. 1.

The general formulation originates from the transport equation expressed in its integral form along a track segment (or chord):

$$\psi_{\text{out}} = \psi_{\text{in}} e^{-\tau} + \frac{q}{\Sigma_t} (1 - e^{-\tau}), \quad (1)$$

where ψ_{in} and ψ_{out} are the entering and exiting angular fluxes, q is the angular source, Σ_t is the total macroscopic cross section, and $\tau = \Sigma_t \ell$ is the optical length. The escape coefficient $E_0(\tau) = 1 - e^{-\tau}$ represents the fraction of the source escaping the segment.

Figure 1. 3D axial tracking scheme: (a) 2D trajectories are placed with radial step (Δ_r); (b) the mesh is extruded to obtain SZ-plane slices; (c) 3D axial tracks are defined with axial step (Δ_s). Adapted from [2].

Figure 2. Example of a 3D trajectory in an extruded geometry. The crossed homogeneous regions are shown together with the local variables q , Σ , and ψ .

The 3D domain is obtained by extruding a non-structured 2D mesh. Tracking is performed in two stages:

- **2D Tracking:** trajectories are generated for a set of azimuthal angles φ .
- **Axial Extrusion:** each 2D trajectory is projected into SZ-planes on which 3D trajectories are traced for each polar angle θ . The axial discretisation does not impose any specific constraint and can be refined independently to control accuracy.

Each trajectory is subdivided into straight chords between material interfaces, and the flux variation

along chord k is

$$\Delta\psi_k = \psi_{\text{out}} - \psi_{\text{in}}. \quad (2)$$

In the TDT formulation, the angular neutron flux is represented using a full space-angle moments expansion:

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, \Omega) \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} A_n(\Omega) \Phi_n(\mathbf{r}), \quad (3)$$

where $A_n(\Omega)$ are real spherical harmonics truncated at order $N_m = (K + 1)^2$ and K is the anisotropy order. Each spatial moment $\Phi_n(\mathbf{r})$ is further expanded *axially* using a polynomial basis:

$$\Phi_n(\mathbf{r}) \approx \sum_{p=0}^{N_p} P_p(\mathbf{r}) \Phi_{n,p,D}, \quad P_p(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\frac{z - z_D}{\Delta z_D / 2} \right)^p, \quad (4)$$

where N_p is the chosen polynomial order, D is the local axial region, Δz_D its height, and z_D its mid-plane. During tracking, each chord contributes to the coefficients $\Phi_{n,p,D}$ through its increment $\Delta\psi_k$ weighted by geometry, spherical harmonics, and axial polynomials. Therefore, unlike classical MOC, the accumulated quantities are not scalar fluxes but the full set of polynomial-harmonic coefficients.

This mathematical structure is naturally parallel: each 3D trajectory can be processed independently. During a sweep, Eq. (1) is solved successively along the chords, with the exiting flux of one chord becoming the entering flux of the next.

In the CUDA implementation, each 3D trajectory is handled by a single GPU thread, and threads are grouped by common 2D trajectory and polar angle.

For symmetry and efficiency, a forward sweep and a backward sweep are performed using the same trajectories, avoiding redundant tracking. This bidirectional sweep is embedded in the outer source-iteration loop, where updated coefficients reconstruct the flux and axial leakage (Fig. 3).

2.2. Parallelisation Workflow from OpenMP to CUDA

The transition from the former OpenMP implementation to CUDA aims to offload the most computationally demanding operations to the GPU while keeping on the CPU only tasks that are executed only once.

Figure 3. Simplified workflow of the 3D MOC GPU implementation: geometry setup and 2D tracking run on the CPU, while the full transport cycle executes on the GPU.

Figure 3 illustrates the new workflow. Pre-transport tasks such as geometry construction and 2D tracking remain on the CPU, whereas the transport computation itself (including source evaluation, sweep-

ing, scalar-flux update, and convergence check) is entirely executed on the GPU. This organisation minimises CPU–GPU data transfers and maximises GPU utilisation.

In previous versions, parallelism relied on OpenMP [2], implemented in Fortran, distributing the work over two dimensions: the set of $2D$ base trajectories traced on the XY-plane and the polar angles θ . The $3D$ trajectories corresponding to each $(2D$ trajectory, θ) pair were swept sequentially by each CPU thread. This strategy is suitable for multi-core CPUs but does not provide enough parallelism for GPUs. The GPU implementation is therefore written in CUDA Fortran, ensuring seamless integration with the existing Fortran-based APOLLO3 code.

To exploit the massive parallelism of modern GPUs, the proposed CUDA implementation introduces a three-level mapping of the TDT workload (Fig. 4):

- (a) *Thread level*: each CUDA thread processes one $3D$ trajectory, performing all end-to-end computations for that path.
- (b) *Block level*: threads are grouped into blocks handling trajectories from the same $(2D$ trajectory, θ) pair, which follow similar geometric paths. This minimises warp divergence and maximises throughput. The block size (768 threads in our case) is tuned to the GPU architecture and register availability.
- (c) *Grid level*: the scheduler prioritises blocks associated with $3D$ trajectories that trace more chords and require more intersection operations. This strategy ensures that heavier blocks are dispatched earlier, allowing lighter ones to fill in the remaining scheduling gaps later on, leading to a more balanced workload and improved overall occupancy.

Figure 4. Hierarchical decomposition of the TDT workload. Each $2D$ base trajectory generates several $3D$ trajectories per polar angle θ . Each $3D$ trajectory is processed by a single CUDA thread; trajectories sharing the same $(2D$ trajectory, θ) pair are grouped within one CUDA block, limiting warp divergence.

This hierarchical organisation provides three key benefits:

- **Scalability**: parallelism increases with the number of $3D$ trajectories, bounded only by the GPU’s thread capacity.
- **Reduced warp divergence**: grouping geometrically similar trajectories within the same block sustains high utilisation of GPU pipelines.
- **Memory coalescence**: adjacent trajectories access contiguous memory regions, enabling efficient memory transactions.

The number of $3D$ trajectories per $(2D$ trajectory, θ) pair depends on the integration step Δ_s . Decreasing Δ_s improves accuracy but increases thread count; performance saturates when active threads exceed the device occupancy limit. A quantitative analysis of this trade-off is presented in Section 3.

3. RESULTS

Two representative test cases were defined based on typical PWR fuel assemblies, arranged in 5×5 and 7×7 configurations. Both geometries are extruded axially and solved using a polynomial flux representation [7]. All simulations were performed with the following configurations:

$$\text{Energy Groups} = 281, \text{Max. Inners} = 20,$$

$$\text{Fission Integral Precision} = 5 \times 10^{-4}, \text{Thermals Precision} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$$

The boundary conditions follow a typical lattice-physics setting: specular reflection on the four radial faces (x_{\min} , x_{\max} , y_{\min} , y_{\max}), vacuum at the bottom (z_{\min}), and specular reflection at the top (z_{\max}). Figures 5 and 6 illustrate both configurations, each simulated to full convergence on CPU and GPU.

Figure 5. 5×5 case geometry.

Figure 6. 7×7 case geometry.

A set of converged simulations was first carried out to verify that the GPU and CPU implementations produce identical physical results. These validation runs were executed on a shared computing cluster using an NVIDIA A100 GPU and an AMD EPYC 9534 @ 2.45GHz (128 threads), under identical stopping criteria and numerical precision. The resulting region-averaged fluxes and reaction-rate distributions match, confirming that the CUDA implementation preserves the physics of the APOLLO3® reference solver. The GPU requires a slightly higher number of inner iterations (3-6%) to reach the same tolerance, which we attribute to round-off effects and to the different ordering of floating-point operations in the convergence check. This numerical detail does not affect the final solution, as both implementations converge to the same flux within machine precision.

Case	Hardware	Parallelism	Δ_s [cm]	Δ_r [cm]	Inners	Outers	Time [s]
5×5	AMD EPYC 9534 (128 threads)	OpenMP	0.015	0.25	1273821	161	165557.23
	NVIDIA A100 (80 Gb)	CUDA	0.015	0.25	1350600	159	129388.67
7×7	AMD EPYC 9534 (128 threads)	OpenMP	0.015	0.25	1396921	166	371795.34
	NVIDIA A100 (80 Gb)	CUDA	0.015	0.25	1434600	164	225649.25

Table I. CPU and GPU produce identical fluxes and reaction-rate distributions for the full-convergence tests.

Because the sweep stage overwhelmingly dominates the total runtime of the 3D transport solver, measuring the time required for a single sweep provides an accurate proxy for the total time-to-solution at convergence. For this reason, a performance comparison for several hardware configurations was carried out using the same 5×5 and 7×7 refinements used in the converged tests, but restricted to one energy group (20 inner iterations) in Figure 7: a single-group sweep is representative of the computational behaviour of a multi-group sweep, as all groups share the same trajectory data structures and memory-access patterns.

Figure 7. Acceleration of various hardware versus the base CPU case for one group iteration.

In the performance plot of Figure 7, two architectures are highlighted in particular: the Intel Xeon Gold 5220R CPU (24 cores and 48 threads per socket, 96 threads in a dual-socket configuration) and the NVIDIA RTX A6000 GPU (84 SMs, 48 GB GDDR6, compute capability 8.6). These correspond to the workstation used throughout the development of the CUDA implementation, and they are the platforms on which all subsequent performance results are obtained. All measurements presented in the next subsection are therefore performed using one inner iteration, which (as previously discussed) provides an accurate proxy for the full time-to-solution, since the sweep dominates the computational cost of the 3D transport solve.

Each GPU kernel launch employed 768 threads per block and one block per streaming multiprocessor (SM). Under this configuration, the scheduler cannot allocate multiple blocks per SM, so the global throughput depends mainly on: (a) the number of available blocks, governed by Δ_r , and (b) the work per block, governed by Δ_s . Both parameters were systematically scanned to evaluate their influence on performance and to characterise the observed saturation behaviour discussed later.

3.1. Acceleration trends

Figure 8 reports the GPU/CPU acceleration as a function of Δ_r and Δ_s for the 5×5 and 7×7 assemblies. *Importantly, these curves compare a single inner iteration on GPU versus the corresponding inner iteration on CPU.* As the sweep dominates the transport cycle, *per-sweep* speed-up is a reliable proxy for the *end-to-end* time-to-solution at convergence, which was independently validated above.

Case 5×5 . Acceleration increases almost monotonically as both Δ_r and Δ_s decrease, reaching a saturation around $10 \times$ for $\Delta_r \leq 0.0075$ and $\Delta_s \leq 0.075$. At coarse discretisations, each block processes few trajectories and remains under-utilised; refining Δ_s adds more 3D trajectories per 2D base track, improving occupancy and concurrency. Once full load is reached, further refinement no longer increases throughput because the kernel becomes dominated by global memory writes rather than arithmetic.

Case 7×7 . The same behaviour is observed, with saturation occurring earlier and at a lower magnitude (around $7.8 \times$). The larger geometry increases memory footprint and the number of updates per region, leading to higher contention and reduced effective concurrency. This reduction is architectural rather than algorithmic.

Origin of the performance saturation

The acceleration increases with spatial refinement until it stabilises around $\sim 10.8 \times$ (5×5) and $\sim 7.8 \times$ (7×7). This limit does not arise from insufficient compute throughput or occupancy, but from the global memory pattern of the flux-accumulation array $\Delta\psi$. Each thread contributes partial flux increments, and this accumulation step dominates kernel cost. Three controlled kernel variants clarify this behaviour: disabling all updates to $\Delta\psi$ makes the kernel about $15 \times$ faster, confirming that runtime is dominated by memory writes; replacing atomics with plain additions ($+=$) further slows execution due to chaotic,

Figure 8. GPU/CPU acceleration for the 5×5 and 7×7 benchmarks under refinement in Δ_r and Δ_s .

non-coalesced stores that trigger L2 invalidations; and using `atomicAdd` is the least costly option thanks to L2 atomic combining, but per-line serialization still limits throughput.

Metric	Atomics ON	Atomics OFF
L2 hit rate — throughput	99.9% — 807 GB/s	63.8% — 120 GB/s
L1/TEX reductions	~95% of all requests	0%
Compute — Memory throughput (SM)	~23% — ~58%	~59% — ~19%
DOMINANT REGIME	LATENCY-BOUND	COMPUTE-BOUND

Table II. Key memory–compute metrics for the 7×7 case (RTX A6000), with and without Δ -reduction.

With Δ -reduction active (performed by atomics), more than 95% of all L2 transactions are atomic reductions, consuming over 90% of peak L2 throughput with near-perfect hit rate. Irregular, non-coalesced writes concentrate on few cache lines: although atomic combining alleviates traffic, cache-line serialization dominates, causing LG Throttle and Long Scoreboard stalls and leaving SM arithmetic units largely under-utilised. When all updates are removed, L2 traffic drops by nearly an order of magnitude and the kernel returns to a compute-bound regime, confirming that the solver currently operates in an *L2-latency-bound atomic regime* where cache-line contention, not arithmetic throughput, sets the performance ceiling.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The GPU-based 3D MOC solver reproduces the CPU reference at convergence for small but representative 3D configurations, confirming full physical consistency of the CUDA implementation. Stable accelerations up to $10\times$ were obtained for finely discretised problems that, while not yet full assemblies, are comparable in numerical scale to forthcoming assembly-level configurations. Larger geometries are expected to exhibit similar computational intensity but an increased number of spatial regions, thus amplifying the very contention mechanism identified as the present performance bottleneck.

The observed performance plateau at fine Δ_r/Δ_s originates not from limited arithmetic throughput or occupancy, but from the structure of global memory updates in the flux accumulation array $\Delta\psi$. These highly irregular and non-coalesced writes cause strong contention in L2 cache: while atomic combining mitigates part of the traffic, per-line serialization persists and produces a latency-bound regime. Nsight Compute profiling identified a dominance of atomic reductions and scheduler stalls (LG Throttle, Long Scoreboard), with arithmetic units largely under-utilised—confirming that the current limit is architectural rather than algorithmic.

The next stage of development must therefore focus on the memory subsystem. Efforts will aim to reduce atomic contention and improve access regularity through redesigned accumulation schemes, local buffering in shared memory, and spatial reordering of trajectories to enhance locality. Such changes directly target the hardware bottleneck exposed here and are essential to scale this solver towards larger, fully extruded geometries while maintaining deterministic reproducibility.

This work thus defines the transition point of the 3D MOC GPU solver: it has reached a regime where computation is extremely parallelised, and further progress depends on mitigating memory-level serialization. By isolating and quantifying this effect, the present study establishes the technical foundation for the next optimisation phase, one that will enable sustained acceleration of large 3D transport workloads within industrial simulation frameworks such as APOLLO3®.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. Mosca, L. Bourhrara, A. Calloo, A. Gammicchia, F. Goubioud, L. Mao, F. Madiot, F. Malouch, E. Masiello, F. Moreau, S. Santandrea, D. Sciannandrone, I. Zmijarevic, E. Y. Garcia-Cervantes, G. Valocchi, J. F. Vidal, F. Damian, P. Laurent, A. Willien, A. Brighenti, L. Graziano, and B. Vezzoni. "APOLLO3®: Overview of the New Code Capabilities for Reactor Physics Analysis." *Nuclear Science and Engineering* (2024). URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00295639.2024.2334992>.
- [2] D. Sciannandrone, S. Santandrea, and R. Sanchez. "Optimized Tracking Strategies for Step MOC Calculations in Extruded 3D Axial Geometries." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 87, pp. 49–60 (2016).
- [3] S. Li, L. Bu, Z. Wang, X. Chi, Z. Ding, et al. "ANT-MOC: Scalable Neutral Particle Transport Using 3-D Method of Characteristics on Multi-GPU Systems." In *Proceedings of SC 2023 – The International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis*, pp. 12:1–12:13. ACM, Denver, CO, USA (2023).
- [4] A. Wang, J. Wang, Z. Ding, X. Geng, and D. Chen. "A Cyclic-Track Decomposition Method for 3-D MOC Neutron Transport Simulation." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, volume 422, p. 113148 (2024).
- [5] W. Kirschenmann, L. Plagne, S. Ploix, A. Ponçot, and S. Vialle. "Massively Parallel Solving of 3-D Simplified PN Equations on Graphics Processing Units." In *Mathematics & Computation, Reactor Physics and Nuclear Applications (M&C 2009)*. Saratoga Springs, NY, USA (2009).
- [6] F. Zhou, S. Li, R. Xue, L. Bu, N. Nie, P. Shi, J. Wang, Y. Hu, et al. "Neutron Particle Transport 3-D Method of Characteristic: Multi-GPU Platform Parallel Computing." arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.17743 (2025). URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.17743>.
- [7] S. Santandrea, L. Graziano, and D. Sciannandrone. "Accelerated polynomial axial expansions for full 3D neutron transport MOC in the APOLLO3 code system as applied to the ASTRID fast breeder reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, volume 113, pp. 194–236 (2018).